

RETAIL DATA ANALYSIS USING CUSTOMERS SEGMENTATION

A

PROJECT PRESENTED

BY

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**IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE COURSE REQUIREMENT IN COMPUTER
SCIENCE.**

MAY, 2021

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the project work entitled “ Retail Data Analysis Using Customers Segmentation” is a collection of my original research work and it has not been presented for any other qualification anywhere. Information from other sources (published or unpublished) has been duly acknowledged.

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CERTIFICATION PAGE

This is to certify that this project work “Retail Data Analysis using Customers Segmentation” was carried out by Ebri Victor Iwara with Matric Number 17283102 meets the regulations governing the award of the degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Science of the University of Abuja and it is approved for its contribution to scientific Knowledge and literary presentation.

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DEDICATION

This project work is dedicated to ALMIGHTY GOD who through his infinite mercy, love, grace, and kindness has been my source of inspiration till the end of this project work, and my wonderful and supporting brother, Daniel Ebri.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I give all thanks to God for the gift of life, infinite love, and the successful completion of this project. My greatest motivators are my Aunt, Dr Anne Ebri. I appreciate your words of encouragement and all of the daily prayers you have said for me. Thank you so much for always being there for me! I appreciate all of my family members that supported me. My deepest appreciation to my wonderful professors, who have accompanied my studies for the last four years, and to my supervisor, Prof. Owolabi Olumide, for all of his support, care, and commitment in guiding me through the composition of my project, you inspired me to become a better professional every day. Thanks to friends and colleagues who gave me the support I needed to get here.

ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the creation of an analytical model for retail data analysis based on consumer segmentation. The goal is to improve promotion efficacy by targeting clients with individualized offers based on their specific interests and habits. The study begins by looking at the significance of data-driven decision-making and the difficulties in digesting massive amounts of retail data. The key issue addressed is the variability of client wants across geographical contexts. To address this, customer segmentation is used as a solution, allowing for the grouping of clients that share similar characteristics. The study's goal is to create an analytical model that uses unsupervised clustering techniques and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce dimensionality.

There are 2240 occurrences and 29 attributes in the collection. The dimensionality of this dataset was lowered before using the clustering algorithm. I developed four clusters and went on to profile the clusters based on their family structure and income/spending. This technique can aid with better marketing strategy planning.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Retail merchants are always researching for methods to make their promotions more effective. Targeting customers with the specific deals most likely to entice them to come back to the store and spend more on their next visit is one approach to do this. Hence, the marketer wants to connect customers with offers in the most appropriate way possible. Making sense of the considerable quantity of data accessible to retailers so they can better understand their customers presents obstacles. Comprehensive store segmentation based on data mining is necessary for successful retail management even though retail analytics is becoming more and more important (Bilgic et al., 2021). This makes retail analytics a field that needs more study. Many firms now prioritize data-driven decision-making and the expanding capabilities of business analytics tools and approaches. Retailers have known for a while that data-driven decision-making might increase the quality of decisions made to boost their business (Kowalczyk & Buxmann, 2015). Retailers seek to adopt a more customer-centric strategy and develop creative methods to comprehend and delight their customers since customer satisfaction affects profitability, which is the key to corporate success. All types of sectors, especially the retail sector, are becoming more and more interested in data analytics since it helps retailers compete by enabling them to provide better customer service. Customer segmentation is an example of retail analytics applications. Customer segmentation is the practice of breaking up your customer base into groups with similar traits, including behaviors or demographics, allowing you to market to those customers more successfully (Segmentation, n.d.). Consumer segmentation discovers various customer groups with distinctive characteristics to better target marketing efforts at each group (Anifa et al., 2022). For a market-driven organization, accurate segmentation increases financial results and the use of organizational resources. A marketer needs to experiment with several segmentation factors (which are: Demographic, Psychographic, Geographic, and Behavioral), either alone or in combination. Hence, any market-driven organization must cater to consumers' diverse wants and preferences with a distinct value proposition (Bose, 2020).

In previous works, the known X, such as demographic information, and an unknown Y—the segments to be identified—in machine learning, segmentation has been done using clustering approaches. The organization needs to understand the four groups that make up the consumer personality (these are: a. Analytical, b. Amiable, c. Expressive, and d. The drivers) to develop distinctive marketing strategies for its products and offerings. Understanding the characteristics of both their customers' and competitors' customers will aid marketers. To further help optimize the potential for a specific commodity or service, segmentation also addresses homogeneity (this means how common or similar the needs of customers are) and heterogeneity (means how different each customer's needs are) of client groupings. Although there are different types of clustering techniques available such as Centroid-based Clustering, Density-based Clustering, Distribution – based Clustering, and Hierarchical Clustering. This project makes use of an agglomerative clustering technique for customer segmentation. It is an example of a hierarchical clustering algorithm. The population is divided into numerous clusters using an unsupervised machine learning technique so that data points within the same cluster are more similar and those within separate clusters are less similar. As it groups each customer into four clusters and profiles them according to their family structure and income/spending for planning a better marketing strategy.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The main concern similar to previous works according to (Anifa et al., 2022) is customers of retail chains tend to have diverse needs all dependent on where they are in the city or country. This is difficult to use a conventional approach to analyze or group these customers. Hence to curb this challenge, customer segmentation can be used and broadened into different behaviors and similarities.

1.3 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

This study aims at developing an analytical model for analyzing retail datasets using customer segmentation. Here is the objective of this project:

- Design of an analytical model for segmenting various Customers
- Implementation of study using an unsupervised clustering technique with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for dimensionality reduction.

- Studying patterns in their clustered form and determining each nature of the clustered pattern.
- Profiling each cluster and determining which customers require more attention.

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

This research is relevant as it aids the critical marketing strategy for organizations and also helps in gaining a competitive advantage. This help in boosting customer relationship with the organization as it means each customer specific needs which will equally increase the sales and profit of the retail organization.

1.5 SCOPE OF STUDY

The scope of this research is restricted to designing an analytical model for retail data analysis using customer segmentation. The dataset is gotten from an open-source site (Kaggle), which consists of customer records from a groceries firm's database. The researcher went as far as making use of data cleaning and feature engineering technique, and data preprocessing to perform the clustering operations. A dimensionality reduction technique (PCA which stands for Principal Component Analysis) and a clustering technique. (Agglomerative clustering) is also included in this research. The application of this project is to be limited to modifying products according to the distinct needs of each customer and the behavioral pattern of such customers. This is to improve the decision-making and also marketing strategy of a firm to help increase customer relationships, demand forecasting, inventory management, sales, and profits.

1.6 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Although this research advances our understanding of the Hopfield–Kagmar (HK) clustering algorithm as an alternative segmentation methodology, it is not without limitations. Given that within-segment variation is the optimization function being minimized, HK may over-fit the data. Thus, in order to more fully assess the performance of HK, it should be evaluated across more real world data sets and validated by comparing HK-based segmentation schemes with actual segmentation outcomes

1.7 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Customer segmentation divides your email lists into groups based on common features that tend to predict buying habits, such as demographics or interests, in order to better serve the customer. This is called a priori segmentation— a priori is Latin for from the former, and basically means that you have deducted these segments based on anecdotal knowledge or observed trends in your marketing efforts. Here are some a priori segments you can use:

- **Demographics:** much of this is publicly-available data that can be gained from your customers during the check-out phase for that first purchase or through other (non-invasive) means: location, age, gender, life stage, marital status. Pro Tip: Facebook and other social media platforms often have much of this information stored on users and can help you build custom audiences for ad outreach.
- **Decision-making status:** especially useful for B2B companies, knowing a customer's job title can make the difference between barking up the wrong tree and making a sale quickly. But decision-making status also works for B2C companies. If you're trying to sell children's products, for example, you'll need to target those with the expendable income (the parents).
- **Customer history with company:** know how long each customer has used your product or followed your brand, which can tell you the most loyal customers, how they've seen you change, and maybe how they'll react to new changes.
- **Personal interactions with customers:** Your support team can help you designate your power users, advocates, and even your difficult tickets. These groups are perfect test segments to start your experiments.

Once you've identified customer groups, you'll want to export or combine those groups into a useable form. Most companies make a list of email addresses that they can use to run an automated email cadence in their email marketing or marketing automation tool. You can also use this list to target on social media, via direct mail, a call cadence, or any other marketing tool you might use. For the sake of simplicity, we'll use a segmented email list as a reference point.

1.8 PROJECT ORGANIZATION

The remainder of this study is as follows:

- Chapter 2 describes various related works based on Retail Data Analysis and Customers Segmentation related academic researches.
- Chapter 3 focuses on the techniques to be used and relevant material for this study.
- Chapter 4 breaks down the result and shows the various steps taken in order to get our result.
- Chapter 5 concludes and results are stated with recommendation for future works.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

This chapter reviews previous research in the field, including a discussion of the strengths and weaknesses of existing methods/approaches of customer segmentation.

Gaining insights into consumer behavior is a valuable marketing strategy that can lead to increased profitability. Companies aim to provide high-quality products or services that meet the needs and wants of their customers, and to do so, they must have a thorough understanding of their customer's preferences and habits (Griva et al., 2018). Thus, information gathering is a crucial asset for companies to maintain customer loyalty. By effectively gathering and analyzing customer information, marketers can provide customized services at every point of interaction, thereby avoiding negative experiences and ensuring customer satisfaction. Retail data analysis using customer segmentation is a crucial marketing strategy involving dividing a customer base into smaller groups based on shared characteristics, such as demographics, psychographics, geographic location, or purchasing behavior, and tailoring marketing efforts towards those groups (Potter, 2014). This approach has become increasingly important in the retail industry as companies seek to create more personalized and relevant marketing campaigns for their customers.

2.1.1 customer segmentation

It is a crucial process for businesses, enabling them to accomplish various goals. One of the most common applications of customer segmentation is to assist marketers in directing marketing campaigns toward specific customers to achieve a specific marketing objective. For example, marketers may use customer segmentation to target customers who have not purchased anything in a while or to encourage existing customers to buy additional items (Ometria, 2016).

Breaking down your customer base into groups based on demographic, and psychographics, amongst other characteristics is known as customer segmentation. There are more reasons to segment your consumer base in addition to marketing. By using customer segmentation in marketing, you may target the appropriate audiences with the appropriate product messaging. Your

marketing campaigns will be more successful as a result of this technique of customer segmentation, also known as client segmentation, which includes:

- Choosing the data that will be acquired and the method for doing so
- Data gathering and integration from numerous sources
- Creating techniques for segmenting data through analysis
- Establishing good communication on the segmentation between pertinent business units (such as marketing and customer service).
- Putting in place programs that deal with data efficiently and react to the information it delivers.

Customer segmentation is commonly performed by analyzing client data sets, which may include segment information or purchase history (Teja, 2022). Various researchers have discussed different customer segmentation techniques in their papers. For instance, Magento⁴ used multiple factors, such as transaction variable, product factor, geographic variable, side interest variable, and page view variable, to perform customer segmentation. Similarly, Baer⁵ and Colica⁶ discussed various customer segmentation techniques, including Business Rule, Supervised Clustering, Unsupervised Clustering, Customer Profiling, Recency, Frequency, monetary value (RFM) Cell Classification Grouping, Customer Likeness Clustering, and Purchase Affinity Clustering, some of which may have similarities (Teja, 2022). Data analysis plays a central role in the customer segmentation process. Retailers use a variety of data sources, including transactional data, website traffic data, and customer feedback, to develop insights into customer behavior and preferences. With this information, they can create customer segments that help identify distinct groups of customers likely to respond to particular marketing messages.

Several methods of customer segmentation have been explored, including demographic segmentation, geographic segmentation, psychographic segmentation, and machine learning based segmentation (Potter, 2014). Demographic segmentation is based on characteristics such as age, gender, income, and education level. Geographic segmentation divides customers by location, such as urban or rural areas. Psychographic segmentation takes into account factors such as personality, values, and lifestyle. Machine learning-based segmentation involves using algorithms to analyze large amounts of data to identify patterns and segment customers based on behavior, interests, and preferences.

In recent years, personalization has emerged as a key component of successful marketing strategies. Personalization involves tailoring marketing messages to individual customers based on their preferences and behaviors. The effectiveness of personalization in marketing strategies has been demonstrated in several studies, with personalized campaigns often outperforming non-personalized ones. Different customer segments have been found to behave differently in terms of brand loyalty, purchasing behavior, and other relevant factors. Understanding these differences is crucial for retailers to create marketing strategies that resonate with different customer segments and drive sales. Marketing strategies that are effective for different customer segments include social media marketing, email marketing, targeted advertising, and loyalty programs. However, it is important to note that not all marketing strategies are equally effective for all customer segments. Understanding the unique characteristics of each segment is crucial for creating successful marketing campaigns (Teja, 2022).

2.2 RETAIL DATA ANALYSIS

Retail data analysis is the process of using statistical and computational methods to analyze data collected by retail businesses (Stubbs, 2018). This type of analysis can help businesses gain insights into customer behavior, sales trends, inventory management, and other factors that can affect their operations. Retail data analysis often involves the collection and processing of large amounts of data from various sources, such as sales records, customer feedback, and demographic information. By analyzing this data, businesses can identify patterns and trends, make informed decisions, and develop strategies to improve their operations and meet the needs of their customers. Retail data analysis enables you to:

- Recognize the behaviors of your clients and modify your offers, strategies, and logistics to better satisfy their needs.
- By engaging in activities that are consistent with your aim, you can increase sales and provide meaningful customer experiences (and even build loyalty).
- Predicting trends, patterns, and seasonal client needs will help you stay on top of demand and inventory by catching little changes you might otherwise miss.

2.3 METHODS FOR CUSTOMER SEGMENTATION

The literature on customer segmentation for retail data analysis has explored various methods, which can be broadly categorized into four main types: demographic, geographic, psychographic, and behavioral segmentation.

- **Demographic segmentation:** This involves segmenting customers based on basic demographic information, such as age, gender, income, education level, and occupation. Demographic segmentation is a widely used method and is useful for identifying broad customer groups, but it may not capture more differences in customer behavioral preferences (Lin, 2002).

(Figure 2.1: A Representation of Demographic Segmentation)

- **Geographic segmentation:** This involves segmenting customers based on their geographic location, such as city, state, region, time zone, climate and season, and cultural preferences. Geographic segmentation can be useful for retailers that have physical stores, as it can help to identify regional trends and preferences (Yieldify, 2020).

(Figure 2.2 Representation of Geographic Segmentation)

- **Psychographic segmentation:** This is a marketing strategy that focuses on the attitudes, opinions, and values of consumers to group them into distinct customer segments. This approach is crucial because it helps to connect the psychological characteristics of consumers with your product or service. By analyzing consumers' perceptions, thoughts, and beliefs, you can gain a better understanding of their needs and preferences, and tailor your marketing efforts accordingly (Wintermeier, n.d.).

(Figure 2.2: Representation of Psychographic Segmentation)

- **Behavioral segmentation:** This involves dividing customers into segments based on their attitudes towards your product, brand, or service, as well as their usage of it, familiarity with your brand and products, and purchasing habits, such as buying only on special occasions like birthdays or holidays. By analyzing these factors, you can gain insights into the specific needs and preferences of each segment (Miakli, 2021).

(Figure 2.3: Representation of Behavioral Segmentation)

Source: <https://www.yieldify.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/types-of-behavioral-segmentation-1110x465.webp>

Some studies have also explored hybrid segmentation methods. Hybrid segmentation is a marketing strategy that blends multiple types of customer segmentation models to create a customized and comprehensive segmentation approach. By combining various segmentation, hybrid segmentation creates a cohesive framework that can be applied across multiple business functions to maximize its impact on your business. This approach offers a unique way to understand your customers, their needs, and preferences, and allows you to develop tailored marketing strategies to reach each segment more effectively.

Common techniques for acquiring information include:

- Telephone interviews or in-person interviews
- Surveys
- General research utilizing available market category information
- Focus sessions

2.4 APPLICATION OF CUSTOMER SEGMENTATION METHODS

There are many examples of how customer segmentation methods have been used in practice to improve the effectiveness of retail data analysis. Some of these examples include the following:

- **Targeted promotions:** Retailers can use customer segmentation data to create targeted promotions that appeal to specific customer segments. For example, a retailer might

create a promotion that is targeted specifically to customers who have previously purchased products in a particular category or who have shown an interest in a particular type of product.

- **Personalized product recommendations:** By analyzing customer segmentation data, retailers can make personalized product recommendations for customers. For example, a retailer might recommend a specific product to a customer based on their previous purchase history or browsing behavior.
- **Tailored marketing campaigns:** Retailers can use customer segmentation data to create tailored marketing campaigns that are designed to appeal to specific customer segments. For example, a retailer might create a marketing campaign that is targeted specifically to customers in a particular geographic region or age group.
- **Product development:** By analyzing customer segmentation data, retailers can gain insight into the specific needs and preferences of different customer segments, which can inform product development strategies. For example, a retailer might develop a new product that is specifically designed to appeal to a particular customer segment, such as millennials or environmentally conscious consumers.
- **Inventory management:** Retailers can use customer segmentation data to inform inventory management strategies. For example, a retailer might stock more of a particular product that is popular among a specific customer segment, or reduce the inventory of a product that is not performing well among a specific customer segment.

2.5 RELATED WORK

The related work on retail data analysis using customer segmentation. The related work is divided into two main categories: customer segmentation methods and applications of customer segmentation in retail.

(Ghasemaghaei & Calic, 2019) gathered data from 280 middle and top-level managers to examine the effects of each big data characteristic (i.e., data volume, data velocity, data variety, and data veracity) on firm innovation competency (i.e., exploitation competency and exploration competency), mediated through data-driven insight generation. Our research was grounded in gestalt insight learning theory and organizational learning theory (i.e., descriptive insight, predictive insight, and prescriptive insight). Findings indicate that while data amount has little bearing on the creation of data-driven insights, data velocity, variety, and authenticity do. The post

hoc analysis's findings also show that while prescriptive insight does not affect innovation competency, descriptive and predictive insight both improve it. These findings offer novel and intriguing theoretical and practical insights.

(Kowalczyk & Buxmann, 2015) In this study, ambidexterity is proposed as a theoretical lens through which to examine data-centric decision support. They identify and explore tensions that result from the conflicting task needs and that present a challenge for efficient BI&A support based on an in-depth multiple case study of BI&A-supported decision processes. They also offer suggestions for how to control these conflicts and develop ambidexterity. They also clarify the connection between ambidexterity and choice quality. They present a theory of ambidexterity in decision support, which explains how such ambidexterity might be supported and how this influences choice outcomes, taking into account the empirical data from this study. Lastly, they discuss how the study affects theory and practice.

(Han et al., 2014) Among those, market segmentation and customer-focused tactics are unquestionably two potent tools that can help significantly ensure rapid and enormous expansion. The goal of this study is to determine how these two tactics affect a successful value chain. To accomplish that, exploratory and qualitative research was conducted. According to the research, market segmentation greatly facilitates the delivery of diversified and personalized goods and services by enabling firms to effectively segment the whole market. In contrast, customer-focus methods also greatly help businesses to concentrate on individual clients and create a market- and client-driven value chain.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 STUDY APPROACH

This study comprises of two phases which are the preprocessing stage and the classification stage. Principal Component Analysis known as PCA is used for the preprocessing of the data, while the Agglomerative Clustering is for categorization.

The Principal Component Analysis is a technique which is put in place for decreasing the dimensionality of datasets while ensuring that the data is kept and readable. This is done by creating new uncorrelated variables while decreasing the variance.

Agglomerative Clustering is a hierarchical clustering technique that requires merging examples till it reaches the desired number of clustered. This study methodology is broken down below:

- Dimensionality reduction using Principal Component Analysis
- Then the use of Agglomerative Clustering Technique for merging the dataset into clusters
- Profiling of customers to determine which customer requires more attention.

Figure 3.1 Shows this study overall design

(Figure 3.1: A System Design)

3.2 EXPERIMENTAL DATASET

In order to achieve the goal of this study, we will make use of a customer's records gotten from a groceries firm database. Here is the dataset:

<https://www.kaggle.com/search?q=customer+segmentation>

.2.1 Dimensionality Reduction Tool

A well-liked unsupervised learning method for lowering the dimensionality of data is principal component analysis. While minimizing information loss, it simultaneously improves interpretability. This makes data easier to plot in 2D and 3D and aids in identifying the dataset's most important properties. Finding a series of linear combinations of variables is made easier by PCA (Waskle et al., 2020).

Algorithm 3.1 PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS (INTERNSHIP, N.D.)

- Get the data to be used
- Data Structuring
- Standardize the Data
- Get Covariance of Z
- Calculate for the Eigen Value and Eigen Vector
- Sort out the Eigen Vectors
- Calculate the new features
- Dispose of unimportant features from the new set

.2.2 Clustering Technique

The most typical hierarchical clustering method often used put objects in clusters based on their resemblance is called agglomerative clustering. Another name for it is AGNES (Agglomerative Nesting). Each object is first treated as a singleton cluster by the algorithm. Once all clusters have been merged into a single large cluster containing all items, pairs of clusters are gradually combined (Addinsoft, 2021). The iterative classification method known as Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering (AHC) operates on a straightforward principal.

Calculating the differences between the N objects initiates the procedure.

- Then, two items are clustered together to form a class that includes these two objects that, when clustered together, minimize a specified agglomeration criterion.
- The agglomeration criterion is then used to determine how different this class is from the N-2 other objects. Then, the two objects or classes of objects are grouped together whose grouping minimizes the agglomeration criterion.

Up till all the items have been grouped, this process is repeated.

Algorithm 3.2: Agglomerative Clustering

- At first, each data point is in its own cluster.
 - Combine the nearest two clusters to create a single cluster.
 - Step 2 should be repeated until you get the required number of clusters.
-

.3 Research Tools

This study makes of Python as its programming language.

3.4 SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

3.4.1 Hardware Configuration

- Processor – Intel® inside Corei7
- Speed – 2.90 GHz
- RAM - 8 GB
- Hard Disk - 20 GB

3.4.2 Software Configuration

- Operating System: Windows 10
- Programming Tool: PYTHON using JUPYTER environment
- Dataset: <https://www.kaggle.com/search?q=customer+segmentation>

3.4.3 Performance Evaluation Metrics

The classifier's performance metrics is assessed based on classification accuracy, The following terms is defined:

$$\text{Accuracy} = (\text{TP} + \text{TN}) / (\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}) \%$$

Accuracy: The possibility that a diagnostic test will be done accurately is known as accuracy. .
(Baratloo et al., 2015)

3.5 SYSTEM SETUP

Due to the tremendous capacity and resilience of JUPYTER, the following are the absolute minimum requirements for compiling the software program. The system specifications are as follows: Windows 7 needed a least of 250GB of hard drive space, 4GB of RAM, and both.

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

4.1 IMPLEMENTATION

4.1.1 Result and Discussion

After developing classification algorithms in Python, classification procedures were carried out on the Google colab platform. In this section, the research results supporting the suggested paradigm are specifically presented. Based on their accuracy percentages, I was able to use and compare them using their performance matrices. Figure 4.1 depicts the Google Colab integrated design area, which is as follows:

(Figure 4.1: A Google Colab Integrated Development Environment)

4.1.2 Importing Libraries

To start the implementation process for this study, I imported these libraries: numpy, pandas, seaborn, datetime, matplotlib, PCA, LableEncoder, and Algometric Clustering. The diagram below shows an illustration of all the libraries imported for the implementation process.

```
[ ] import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns

from datetime import datetime

from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler

from sklearn.decomposition import PCA #for dimensionality reduction (PCA)

from sklearn.cluster import KMeans

# to display plots in Jupyter notebook or IPython
%matplotlib inline

from mpl_toolkits.mplot3d import Axes3D #for 3d visualization

# optional: suppress warnings
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
```

(Figure 4.2: Diagram Illustrating the Imported Libraries).

4.1.3 Loading the Dataset

I made use of the panda's library for the importation of the CSV file. Here the *"pd.read csv"* was written to make this possible. The flag at the end of the code (csv), indicates that only documents in comma-separated values are permitted to be read into the model. The dataset used in the cause of this study consists of 2240 instances and 29 attributes. The diagram below in Figure 4.3 shows that 5 rows of the dataset were returned after inputting the line of code titled *"customer_data.head()"*. Hence this brought out a dataset consisting of 5 rows and 29 columns.

```

LOADING DATA

[ ] customer_data = pd.read_csv('/kaggle/input/customer-personality-analysis/marketing_campaign.csv', delimiter='\t')
customer_data.head(5)

```

	ID	Year_Birth	Education	Marital_Status	Income	Kidhome	Teenhome	Dt_Customer	Recency	MntWines	...	NumWebVisitsMonth	AcceptedCmp3	AcceptedCmp4	AcceptedCmp5	AcceptedCmp1	AcceptedCmp2	Complain	Z_CostContac
0	5524	1957	Graduation	Single	58138.0	0	0	04-09-2012	88	635	...	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	2174	1954	Graduation	Single	46344.0	1	1	08-03-2014	38	11	...	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	4141	1965	Graduation	Together	71613.0	0	0	21-08-2013	26	426	...	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	6182	1984	Graduation	Together	26646.0	1	0	10-02-2014	26	11	...	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	5324	1981	PhD	Married	58293.0	1	0	19-01-2014	94	173	...	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

5 rows x 29 columns

(Figure 4.3: Diagram Illustrating the Loaded Dataset.)

4.1.4 Data Cleaning

This section consists of two distinct phases which are Data cleaning and Feature Engineering. To clean the dataset, I needed to under the data itself. Hence, I made use of “*data.info ()*” to read out the contents of the dataset. From the diagram below it was concluded that:

- The dataset consisted of missing values
- It also indicated that the customers that joined the database in the Income Dt_Customer section are not as organized as that in the Date Time.
- Our data frame contains some categorical features, just as dtype: object contains some. As a result, we'll have to encode them into numeric forms later.

Figure 4.4 shows the information of the dataset.

```

▶ #Information on features
data.info()

<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 2240 entries, 0 to 2239
Data columns (total 29 columns):
#   Column                                Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  -
0   ID                                     2240 non-null   int64
1   Year_Birth                             2240 non-null   int64
2   Education                               2240 non-null   object
3   Marital_Status                         2240 non-null   object
4   Income                                  2216 non-null   float64
5   Kidhome                                 2240 non-null   int64
6   Teenhome                                2240 non-null   int64
7   Dt_Customer                             2240 non-null   object
8   Recency                                  2240 non-null   int64
9   MntWines                                 2240 non-null   int64
10  MntFruits                                 2240 non-null   int64
11  MntMeatProducts                         2240 non-null   int64
12  MntFishProducts                         2240 non-null   int64
13  MntSweetProducts                       2240 non-null   int64
14  MntGoldProds                            2240 non-null   int64
15  NumDealsPurchases                      2240 non-null   int64
16  NumWebPurchases                        2240 non-null   int64
17  NumCatalogPurchases                   2240 non-null   int64
18  NumStorePurchases                     2240 non-null   int64
19  NumWebVisitsMonth                     2240 non-null   int64
20  AcceptedCmp3                          2240 non-null   int64
21  AcceptedCmp4                          2240 non-null   int64
22  AcceptedCmp5                          2240 non-null   int64
23  AcceptedCmp1                          2240 non-null   int64
24  AcceptedCmp2                          2240 non-null   int64
25  Complain                                2240 non-null   int64
26  Z_CostContact                          2240 non-null   int64
27  Z_Revenue                              2240 non-null   int64
28  Response                                2240 non-null   int64
dtypes: float64(1), int64(25), object(3)
memory usage: 507.6+ KB

```

(Figure 4.4: Diagram Illustrating the Dataset Information)

After gaining the dataset information I went forward to drop the rows that had missing income information. After the removal of the process, I was left with a total of 2216 available values in the dataset as compared to its original values of 2239 values. Below is a graphical representation of this statement.

```

[ ] #To remove the NA values
data = data.dropna()
print("The total number of data-points after removing the rows with missing values are:", len(data))

The total number of data-points after removing the rows with missing values are: 2216

```

(Figure 4.5: Diagram Illustrating Removed Values).

In the next step, I will make a feature out of "Dt_Customer" that shows how long a customer has been registered in the firm's database. To keep things simple, I am taking this value relative to the most recent customer in the record. To obtain the values, I must first check the most recent and oldest recorded dates.

```
data["Dt_Customer"] = pd.to_datetime(data["Dt_Customer"])
dates = []
for i in data["Dt_Customer"]:
    i = i.date()
    dates.append(i)
#Dates of the newest and oldest recorded customer
print("The newest customer's enrolment date in therecords:",max(dates))
print("The oldest customer's enrolment date in the records:",min(dates))
```

The newest customer's enrolment date in therecords: 2014-12-06
The oldest customer's enrolment date in the records: 2012-01-08

(Figure 4.6: Diagram Illustrating Customers Records).

I will be adding a feature ("Customer_For") to track the number of days customers began shopping in the store relative to the last recorded date.

```
[ ] #Created a feature "Customer_For"
days = []
d1 = max(dates) #taking it to be the newest customer
for i in dates:
    delta = d1 - i
    days.append(delta)
data["Customer_For"] = days
data["Customer_For"] = pd.to_numeric(data["Customer_For"], errors="coerce")
```

(Figure 4.6: Diagram Illustrating Customers Records).

To gain a better understanding of the data, I investigated the unique values in the categorical features. This brought out the total number of customers in both the marital status section and the education section.

```

▶ print("Total categories in the feature Marital_Status:\n", data["Marital_Status"].value_counts(), "\n")
print("Total categories in the feature Education:\n", data["Education"].value_counts())

Total categories in the feature Marital_Status:
Married      857
Together     573
Single       471
Divorced     232
Widow        76
Alone         3
Absurd        2
YOLO          2
Name: Marital_Status, dtype: int64

Total categories in the feature Education:
Graduation   1116
PhD           481
Master       365
2n Cycle     200
Basic         54
Name: Education, dtype: int64

```

(Figure 4.6: Diagram Illustrating Customers Values in both Marital Status and Education).

4.1.5 Feature Engineering

In the next bit, I will perform the following steps to engineer some new features:

- Extract the "Age" of a customer by the "Year_Birth" indicating the birth year of the respective person.
- Create another feature "Spent" indicating the total amount spent by the customer in various categories over two years.
- Create another feature "Living_With" out of "Marital_Status" to extract the living situation of couples.
- Create a feature "Children" to indicate the total number of children in a household that is, kids and teenagers.
- To get further clarity on a household, Create a feature indicating "Family_Size"
- Create a feature "Is_Parent" to indicate the parenthood status
- Lastly, I will create three categories in "Education" by simplifying its value counts.
- Dropping some of the redundant features

The diagram below shows the implementation of the above steps.

```
[ ] #Feature Engineering
#Age of customer today
data["Age"] = 2021-data["Year_Birth"]

#Total spendings on various items
data["Spent"] = data["MntWines"]+ data["MntFruits"]+ data["MntMeatProducts"]+ data["MntFishProducts"]+ data["MntSweetProducts"]+ data["MntGoldProds"]

#Deriving living situation by marital status"Alone"
data["Living_With"]=data["Marital_Status"].replace({"Married":"Partner", "Together":"Partner", "Absurd":"Alone", "Widow":"Alone", "YOLO":"Alone", "Divorced":"Alone", "Single":"Alone",})

#Feature indicating total children living in the household
data["Children"]=data["Kidhome"]+data["Teenhome"]

#Feature for total members in the household
data["Family_Size"] = data["Living_With"].replace({"Alone": 1, "Partner":2})+ data["Children"]

#Feature pertaining parenthood
data["Is_Parent"] = np.where(data.Children> 0, 1, 0)

#Segmenting education levels in three groups
data["Education"]=data["Education"].replace({"Basic":"Undergraduate", "2n Cycle":"Undergraduate", "Graduation":"Graduate", "Master":"Postgraduate", "PhD":"Postgraduate"})

#For clarity
data=data.rename(columns={"MntWines": "Wines", "MntFruits": "Fruits", "MntMeatProducts": "Meat", "MntFishProducts": "Fish", "MntSweetProducts": "Sweets", "MntGoldProds": "Gold"})

#Dropping some of the redundant features
to_drop = ["Marital_Status", "Ot_Customer", "z_CostContact", "z_Revenue", "Year_Birth", "ID"]
data = data.drop(to_drop, axis=1)
```

(Figure 4.6: Feature Engineering steps).

4.1.6 Data Description

Data is used to describing datasets in the program. The describe() function computes statistical statistics for the numerical values in a data frame, such as the mean, percentile, and standard deviation (std). This dataset's count, mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, and percentiles of 25 percent, 50 percent, and 75 percent were calculated. Figure 4.7 depicts the data description for the Lung Cancer dataset.

data.describe()

	Income	Kidhome	Teenhome	Recency	wines	Fruits	Meat	Fish	Sweets	Gold	...	AcceptedCmp1	AcceptedCmp2	Complain	Response	Customer_For
count	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	...	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	2216.000000	2.216000e+03
mean	52247.251354	0.441787	0.505415	49.012635	305.091606	26.356047	166.995939	37.637635	27.028881	43.965253	...	0.064079	0.013538	0.009477	0.150271	4.423735e+16
std	25173.076661	0.536896	0.544181	28.948352	337.327920	39.793917	224.283273	54.782082	41.072046	51.815414	...	0.244950	0.115388	0.096907	0.357417	2.008532e+16
min	1730.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	...	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000e+00
25%	35303.000000	0.000000	0.000000	24.000000	24.000000	2.000000	16.000000	3.000000	1.000000	9.000000	...	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	2.937600e+16
50%	51381.500000	0.000000	0.000000	49.000000	174.500000	8.000000	68.000000	12.000000	8.000000	24.500000	...	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	4.432320e+16
75%	68522.000000	1.000000	1.000000	74.000000	505.000000	33.000000	232.250000	50.000000	33.000000	56.000000	...	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	5.927040e+16
max	666666.000000	2.000000	2.000000	99.000000	1493.000000	199.000000	1725.000000	259.000000	262.000000	321.000000	...	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	9.184320e+16

8 rows x 28 columns

(Figure 4.7: Diagram Showing The Data Description)

The above statistics show some disparities in mean and maximum income and age. Please keep in mind that the maximum age is 128 years because I calculated the age as of today (that is., 2023) and the data is old. I need to take a broader look at the data. I will draw some of the chosen features. Below is a pairplot showing the values of the income, recency, customer_for, Age, Spent, and Is_parent which are all part of the attributes of this dataset.

(Figure 4.8: PairPlot of some of the Dataset Attributes).

From the above result, I noticed that there are a few outliers in the Income and Age features. I will be deleting the outliers in the data. After this process, the total number of data points equates to 2212.

```
#Dropping the outliers by setting a cap on Age and income.
data = data[(data["Age"]<90)]
data = data[(data["Income"]<600000)]
print("The total number of data-points after removing the outliers are:", len(data))
```

The total number of data-points after removing the outliers are: 2212.

(Figure 4.9: New Values of Data Points).

4.1.7 Data Correlation

Next, let us look at the correlation among the features. (Excluding the categorical attributes at this point). Using the dataset's instances, I created a Pearson correlation plot. I created a Pearson chart with the row and quantity data. I used the imported seaborn and set the correlation plot size to (16,12) and the font size to 20. Figure 4.10 depicts a graphical representation of the heatmap.

(Figure 4.9: Diagram Illustrating the Pearson Correlation Plot).

The data is relatively clean, and the new features have been implemented. I'll move on to the next step. That is, data preprocessing.

4.1.8 preprocessing of data

In this section, I will preprocess the data in preparation for clustering operations. The data is preprocessed using the following steps:

- The label encoding categorical features
- Using the standard scaler to scale the features
- Creating a subset data frame to reduce the dimensionality

```
#Get list of categorical variables
s = (data.dtypes == 'object')
object_cols = list(s[s].index)

print("Categorical variables in the dataset:", object_cols)

Categorical variables in the dataset: ['Education', 'Living_with']

[ ] #Label Encoding the object dtypes.
LE=LabelEncoder()
for i in object_cols:
    data[i]=data[[i]].apply(LE.fit_transform)

print("All features are now numerical")

All features are now numerical

[ ] #Creating a copy of data
ds = data.copy()
# creating a subset of dataframe by dropping the features on deals accepted and promotions
cols_del = ['AcceptedCmp3', 'AcceptedCmp4', 'AcceptedCmp5', 'AcceptedCmp1', 'AcceptedCmp2', 'Complain', 'Response']
ds = ds.drop(cols_del, axis=1)
#Scaling
scaler = StandardScaler()
scaler.fit(ds)
scaled_ds = pd.DataFrame(scaler.transform(ds), columns= ds.columns )
print("All features are now scaled")

All features are now scaled
```

(Figure 4.10: Diagram Illustrating the steps in Preprocessing the Dataset).

Here is the scaled data that will be used by the PCA model for dimensionality reduction.

```

#Scaled data to be used for reducing the dimensionality
print("Dataframe to be used for further modelling:")
scaled_ds.head()

```

Dataframe to be used for further modelling:

	Education	Income	Kidhome	Teenhome	Recency	Wines	Fruits	Meat	Fish	Sweets	...	NumCatalogPurchases	NumStorePurchases	NumWebVisitsMonth	Customer_For	Age	Spent	Living_Mith	Children
0	-0.893586	0.287105	-0.822754	-0.929699	0.310353	0.977660	1.552041	1.690293	2.453472	1.483713	...	2.503607	-0.555814	0.692181	1.973583	1.018352	1.676245	-1.349603	-1.264598
1	-0.893586	-0.260882	1.040021	0.908097	-0.380813	-0.672618	-0.637461	-0.718230	-0.651004	-0.634019	...	-0.571340	-1.171160	-0.132545	-1.665144	1.274785	-0.963297	-1.349603	1.404572
2	-0.893586	0.913196	-0.822754	-0.929699	-0.795514	0.357935	0.570540	-0.178542	1.339513	-0.147184	...	-0.229679	1.290224	-0.544908	-0.172664	0.334530	0.280110	0.740959	-1.264598
3	-0.893586	-1.176114	1.040021	-0.929699	-0.795514	-0.672618	-0.561961	-0.655787	-0.504911	-0.585335	...	-0.913000	-0.555814	0.279818	-1.923210	-1.289547	-0.920135	0.740959	0.069987
4	0.571657	0.294307	1.040021	-0.929699	1.554453	-0.392257	0.419540	-0.218684	0.152508	-0.001133	...	0.111982	0.059532	-0.132545	-0.822130	-1.033114	-0.307562	0.740959	0.069987

5 rows x 23 columns

(Figure 4.11: Diagram Illustrating the Dataset used for Dimensionality Reduction).

4.1.9 Dimensionality Reduction (PCA)

There are numerous factors in this issue that will be used to determine the final classification. These elements are essentially characteristics or features. The more features there are, the more challenging it is to use. Many of these characteristics are redundant because they are correlated. This is why, prior to running the features through a classifier, I will perform dimensionality reduction on the chosen features. By obtaining a set of principal variables, dimensionality reduction is the process of reducing the number of random variables being considered.

A method for reducing the dimensionality of such datasets, improving interpretability while minimizing information loss is principal component analysis (PCA). The following actions:

- PCA-based dimension reduction
- Graphing the compressed dataframe

Dimensionality reduction with PCA

For this project, I will be reducing the dimensions to 3.

A 3D Projection Of Data In The Reduced Dimension

(Figure 4.11: Diagram Illustrating the Projection of Dataset in a Reduced Form).

4.1.10 Clustering Technique

Steps involved in the Clustering Elbow Method to determine the number of clusters to be formed
Clustering via Agglomerative Clustering Examining the clusters formed via scatter plot Now that the attributes have been reduced to three dimensions, I will perform clustering via Agglomerative clustering, which is a hierarchical clustering method.

```

▶ # Quick examination of elbow method to find numbers of clusters to make.
print('Elbow Method to determine the number of clusters to be formed:')
Elbow_M = KElbowVisualizer(KMeans(), k=10)
Elbow_M.fit(PCA_ds)
Elbow_M.show()

```

▶ Elbow Method to determine the number of clusters to be formed:

(Figure 4.12: Diagram Illustrating Number of Clusters to be Formed).

Four clusters are the ideal number for this set of data, according to the cell above. The final clusters will be obtained by fitting the agglomerative clustering model next. After this the agglomerative clustering model is initiated and the model is fit in and afterwards added to the original dataframe. I will look at the clusters' 3-D distribution to analyze the clusters that have formed. Below represents the plotted clusters.

(Figure 4.13: Diagram Illustrating the Clusters)

4.2 MODEL EVALUATION

Since this clustering was done without supervision. This model cannot be evaluated or scored because it lacks a tagged feature. This section's goal is to examine the patterns in the clusters that have formed and ascertain their nature.

In order to do that, I will use exploratory data analysis to look at the data in the context of clusters and make judgments. Let's look at the group distribution of the clustering first.

```
[ ] #Plotting countplot of clusters
pal = ["#682F2F", "#B9C0C9", "#9F8A78", "#F3AB60"]
pl = sns.countplot(x=data["clusters"], palette= pal)
pl.set_title("Distribution Of The Clusters")
plt.show()
```


(Figure 4.14: Barchart Illustrating the Plotted Clusters)

The diagram below shows a scattered plot of a fairly distributed cluster.

```
[ ] pl = sns.scatterplot(data = data,x=data["Spent"], y=data["Income"],hue=data["Clusters"], palette= pal)
pl.set_title("Cluster's Profile Based On Income And Spending")
plt.legend()
plt.show()
```


(Figure 4.15: Clustered Profile of Customers based on Income and Spending).

The clusters pattern is displayed on the income vs. spending plot. High spending and average income are represented by group 0, high spending and high income by group 1, low spending and low income by group 2, and high spending and low income by group 3. I will then examine the precise distribution of clusters according to the different products in the data. the following: Wines, Fruits, Meat, Fish, Sweets, and Gold.

```
[ ] plt.figure()
    pl=sns.swarmplot(x=data["Clusters"], y=data["Spent"], color= "#CBEDDD", alpha=0.5 )
    pl=sns.boxenplot(x=data["Clusters"], y=data["Spent"], palette=pal)
    plt.show()
```


Figure 4.15: Swarm Plot showing Detailed Distribution Clusters.

The above plot makes it clear that cluster 1 is our largest group of customers, followed closely by cluster 0. For the targeted marketing strategies, I can investigate what each cluster spends money on.

4.3 RESULT OF MODELS

The following information can be deduced about the customers in different clusters. Figure 4.16 describes it.

(Figure 4.16: A Digram of the Profiled Clusters).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 SUMMARY

Many businesses are focusing on the increasing capabilities of business analytics tools and techniques, as well as data-driven decision-making. Retailers have long recognized that data-driven decision-making can improve decision quality (Kowalczyk & Buxmann, 2015). Because customer satisfaction affects profitability, which is the key to business success, retailers want to adopt a more customer-centric approach and discover new ways to understand and satisfy their customers. In order to improve the retail detail analysis, this study makes use of PCA and an agglomerative clustering system to perform customer segmentation.

In order to design an analytical mode for segmenting various customers, I had to implement an agglomerative clustering alongside a dimensionality reduction technique (PCA). The dataset utilized for this study was obtained from an open dataset (Kaggle). The dataset consist of 2240 instances and 29 attributes. This dataset dimensionality was reduced followed by the clustering technique. Here I came up with four clusters and I went further to profile the clusters according to their family structure and income/spending. This technique can help in better planning of the marketing strategy.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The suggested method adds to the body of knowledge on creating and using efficient decision support systems based on retail analytics. The primary innovation of this study is the provision of a novel retail analytics approach utilizing PCA and agglomerative clustering for Purchasing Behavior Analysis. In contrast to other studies, the proposed approach does not necessitate the definition of new complex algorithms for cluster analysis and association rule mining.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION

In addition to future replications, the survey, consumer preferences, and choices can be taken into account when selecting products and performing a conjoint analysis to better segment customers.

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APPENDIX

IMPORTING LIBRARIES

```
#Importing the Libraries
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import datetime
import matplotlib
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from matplotlib import colors
import seaborn as sns
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
from sklearn.decomposition import PCA
from yellowbrick.cluster import KElbowVisualizer
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt, numpy as np
from mpl_toolkits.mplot3d import Axes3D
from sklearn.cluster import AgglomerativeClustering
from matplotlib.colors import ListedColormap
from sklearn import metrics
import warnings
import sys
if not sys.warnoptions:
    warnings.simplefilter("ignore")
np.random.seed(42)
```

LOADING DATA

```

#Loading the dataset
data = pd.read_csv("../input/customer-personality-analysis/marketing_campaign.csv", sep="\t")
print("Number of datapoints:", len(data))

data.head()

#Information on features
data.info()

#To remove the NA values
data = data.dropna()

print("The total number of data-
points after removing the rows with missing values are:", len(data))

data["Dt_Customer"] = pd.to_datetime(data["Dt_Customer"])
dates = []

for i in data["Dt_Customer"]:
    i = i.date()
    dates.append(i)

#Dates of the newest and oldest recorded customer
print("The newest customer's enrolment date in therecords:",max(dates))
print("The oldest customer's enrolment date in the records:",min(dates))

#Created a feature "Customer_For"
days = []

d1 = max(dates) #taking it to be the newest customer

for i in dates:
    delta = d1 - i
    days.append(delta)

data["Customer_For"] = days

data["Customer_For"] = pd.to_numeric(data["Customer_For"], errors="coerce")

print("Total categories in the feature Marital_Status:\n", data["Marital_Status"].value_counts(), "\n")
print("Total categories in the feature Education:\n", data["Education"].value_counts())

#Feature Engineering
#Age of customer today

```

```
data["Age"] = 2021-data["Year_Birth"]
```

```
#Total spendings on various items
```

```
data["Spent"] = data["MntWines"]+ data["MntFruits"]+ data["MntMeatProducts"]+ data["MntFishProducts"]+ data["MntSweetProducts"]+ data["MntGoldProds"]
```

```
#Deriving living situation by marital status"Alone"
```

```
data["Living_With"]=data["Marital_Status"].replace({"Married":"Partner", "Together":"Partner", "Absurd":"Alone", "Widow":"Alone", "YOLO":"Alone", "Divorced":"Alone", "Single":"Alone"},})
```

```
#Feature indicating total children living in the household
```

```
data["Children"]=data["Kidhome"]+data["Teenhome"]
```

```
#Feature for total members in the household
```

```
data["Family_Size"] = data["Living_With"].replace({"Alone": 1, "Partner":2})+ data["Children"]
```

```
#Feature pertaining parenthood
```

```
data["Is_Parent"] = np.where(data.Children> 0, 1, 0)
```

```
#Segmenting education levels in three groups
```

```
data["Education"]=data["Education"].replace({"Basic":"Undergraduate", "2n Cycle":"Undergraduate", "Graduation":"Graduate", "Master":"Postgraduate", "PhD":"Postgraduate"})
```

```
#For clarity
```

```
data=data.rename(columns={"MntWines": "Wines", "MntFruits":"Fruits", "MntMeatProducts":"Meat", "MntFishProducts":"Fish", "MntSweetProducts":"Sweets", "MntGoldProds":"Gold"})
```

```
#Dropping some of the redundant features
```

```
to_drop = ["Marital_Status", "Dt_Customer", "Z_CostContact", "Z_Revenue", "Year_Birth", "ID"]
```

```

data = data.drop(to_drop, axis=1)

data.describe()
#To plot some selected features
#Setting up colors preferences

sns.set(rc={"axes.facecolor": "#FFF9ED", "figure.facecolor": "#FFF9ED"})

pallet = ["#682F2F", "#9E726F", "#D6B2B1", "#B9C0C9", "#9F8A78", "#F3AB60"]

cmap = colors.ListedColormap(["#682F2F", "#9E726F", "#D6B2B1", "#B9C0C9", "#9F8A78",
"#F3AB60"])

#Plotting following features

To_Plot = [ "Income", "Recency", "Customer_For", "Age", "Spent", "Is_Parent"]

print("Relative Plot Of Some Selected Features: A Data Subset")

plt.figure()

sns.pairplot(data[To_Plot], hue= "Is_Parent", palette= (["#682F2F", "#F3AB60"]))

#Taking hue

plt.show()

#Dropping the outliers by setting a cap on Age and income.
data = data[(data["Age"]<90)]

data = data[(data["Income"]<600000)]

print("The total number of data-points after removing the outliers are:", len(data))

#correlation matrix
corrmat= data.corr()

plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))

sns.heatmap(corrmat,annot=True, cmap=cmap, center=0)

#Get list of categorical variables
s = (data.dtypes == 'object')

object_cols = list(s[s].index)

print("Categorical variables in the dataset:", object_cols)

#Label Encoding the object dtypes.
LE=LabelEncoder()

for i in object_cols:
    data[i]=data[[i]].apply(LE.fit_transform)

```

```

print("All features are now numerical")

#Creating a copy of data
ds = data.copy()

# creating a subset of dataframe by dropping the features on deals accepted and promotions
cols_del = ['AcceptedCmp3', 'AcceptedCmp4', 'AcceptedCmp5', 'AcceptedCmp1','AcceptedCmp
2', 'Complain', 'Response']

ds = ds.drop(cols_del, axis=1)

#Scaling
scaler = StandardScaler()
scaler.fit(ds)
scaled_ds = pd.DataFrame(scaler.transform(ds),columns= ds.columns )
print("All features are now scaled")

#Scaled data to be used for reducing the dimensionality
print("Dataframe to be used for further modelling:")
scaled_ds.head()

#Initiating PCA to reduce dimentions aka features to 3
pca = PCA(n_components=3)
pca.fit(scaled_ds)
PCA_ds = pd.DataFrame(pca.transform(scaled_ds), columns=(["col1", "col2", "col3"]))
PCA_ds.describe().T

#A 3D Projection Of Data In The Reduced Dimension
x =PCA_ds["col1"]
y =PCA_ds["col2"]
z =PCA_ds["col3"]

#To plot
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(10,8))
ax = fig.add_subplot(111, projection="3d")
ax.scatter(x,y,z, c="maroon", marker="o" )
ax.set_title("A 3D Projection Of Data In The Reduced Dimension")
plt.show()

```

```

# Quick examination of elbow method to find numbers of clusters to make.
print('Elbow Method to determine the number of clusters to be formed:')

Elbow_M = KElbowVisualizer(KMeans(), k=10)

Elbow_M.fit(PCA_ds)

Elbow_M.show()

#Initiating the Agglomerative Clustering model
AC = AgglomerativeClustering(n_clusters=4)

# fit model and predict clusters
yhat_AC = AC.fit_predict(PCA_ds)
PCA_ds["Clusters"] = yhat_AC

#Adding the Clusters feature to the original dataframe.
data["Clusters"]= yhat_AC

#Plotting the clusters
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(10,8))

ax = plt.subplot(111, projection='3d', label="bla")

ax.scatter(x, y, z, s=40, c=PCA_ds["Clusters"], marker='o', cmap = cmap )

ax.set_title("The Plot Of The Clusters")

plt.show()

#Plotting countplot of clusters
pal = ["#682F2F", "#B9C0C9", "#9F8A78", "#F3AB60"]

pl = sns.countplot(x=data["Clusters"], palette= pal)

pl.set_title("Distribution Of The Clusters")

plt.show()

pl = sns.scatterplot(data = data,x=data["Spent"], y=data["Income"],hue=data["Clusters"], palette
= pal)
pl.set_title("Cluster's Profile Based On Income And Spending")

plt.legend()

plt.show()

plt.figure()
pl=sns.swarmplot(x=data["Clusters"], y=data["Spent"], color= "#CBEDDD", alpha=0.5 )

pl=sns.boxenplot(x=data["Clusters"], y=data["Spent"], palette=pal)

plt.show()

```

```

#Creating a feature to get a sum of accepted promotions
data["Total_Promos"] = data["AcceptedCmp1"]+ data["AcceptedCmp2"]+ data["AcceptedCmp3"]+ data["AcceptedCmp4"]+ data["AcceptedCmp5"]

#Plotting count of total campaign accepted.

plt.figure()

pl = sns.countplot(x=data["Total_Promos"],hue=data["Clusters"], palette= pal)

pl.set_title("Count Of Promotion Accepted")

pl.set_xlabel("Number Of Total Accepted Promotions")

plt.show()

#Plotting the number of deals purchased
plt.figure()

pl=sns.boxenplot(y=data["NumDealsPurchases"],x=data["Clusters"], palette= pal)

pl.set_title("Number of Deals Purchased")

plt.show()

#for more details on the purchasing style
Places=["NumWebPurchases", "NumCatalogPurchases", "NumStorePurchases", "NumWebVisitsMonth"]

for i in Places:

    plt.figure()

    sns.jointplot(x=data[i],y = data["Spent"],hue=data["Clusters"], palette= pal)

    plt.show()

Personal = [ "Kidhome","Teenhome","Customer_For", "Age", "Children", "Family_Size", "Is_Parent", "Education","Living_With"]

for i in Personal:

    plt.figure()

    sns.jointplot(x=data[i], y=data["Spent"], hue =data["Clusters"], kind="kde", palette=pal)

    plt.show()

```